

Scelotes sexlineatus Striped Dwarf Burrowing Skink

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: 10 - 20 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

Endemic to the Republic of South Africa, occurring in Little Namaqualand from Port Nolloth to Clanwilliam.

Importance:

It serves as an important model species for studying specific stages of limb development within the genus *Scelotes*, representing an intermediate limb development stage (forelimb digits = 0; hindlimb digits = 2), and for investigating the genomic evolution of vertebrates. It has a restricted distribution and occurs in distinct habitats and regions, making it an excellent model species for biogeographic and molecular ecology studies.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 48.66 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.93 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 1.56 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.8% [Single: 96.9%, Duplicated: 2.0%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 1 438.34 kilobases

Contig number: 6 180

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